

KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES

eifl 2023
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2023, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 37 countries and ran projects in an additional 17 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 54 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

CONTENTS

WHERE WE WORK	2
WHO WE ARE	5
DIRECTOR'S REPORT	6
FACILITATING THE OPEN SHARING OF RESEARCH	7
MEET THE PEOPLE	10
OUR NETWORK	15
OUR TEAM	17
FINANCIAL REPORT	18
OUR FUNDERS	18
EVENTS	19
OUR PARTNERS	21
STAY CONNECTED	23

**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

Welcome to the creativity Library

 @proeivan
@bibliotecadelacreatividad

Ivan Eduardo Triana Bohoquez, Director General at Fundación Biblioeseo in Colombia, gives an ignite talk at Dokk1, Aarhus City Library, Denmark, in May 2023. The library won an EIFL Public Library Innovation Award for Enabling learning through play.

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

Our strategy has three main goals:

To advance a fair and sustainable transition from paywalled to open access content

Major achievements in 2023 —

- 14 agreements with publishers were in place enabling authors from EIFL partner countries to publish for free, or at reduced prices, in open access in 2,545 journals. 1,446 authors benefited from these agreements and they published 1,746 articles in open access. Savings in Article Processing Charges (APCs) for authors and their institutions amounted to US\$2,574,893.
- Read & Publish agreements, in which researchers can access journals and also publish articles in open access without paying APCs: In 2023, Estonia, Fiji, Ghana, Latvia, Lithuania and Palestine signed up for the EIFL-negotiated agreement with Cambridge University Press, and Latvia and Slovenia joined the agreement with SAGE Publications.
- We provided advice to governments and institutions that were developing open access policies.
 - Three national policies (in Botswana, 1; Slovenia, 2) and five institutional policies (in Kenya and Serbia) were adopted mandating deposit of research output in open access repositories.

To support research, teaching and learning

Major achievements in 2023 —

- We released a 3rd edition of the 'EIFL Digital Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians'.

- Organized two five-day online EIFL Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps attended by 136 trainers from 29 EIFL partner countries, and released bootcamp material as an open resource.
- Supported the strengthening of open science trainers in Europe, by hosting two OpenAIRE train-the-trainer bootcamps.
- We advocated for national copyright law reform to encourage the adoption of modern copyright laws that maximize access to content:
 - Participated in copyright law reviews in nine countries — Kenya, Moldova, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Uganda, Ukraine and Zimbabwe.
 - Contributed to ending the book famine for persons with print disabilities by supporting ratification and domestication of the Marrakesh Treaty in five countries — Armenia, Kenya, Kosovo, Moldova, Uganda and Ukraine.
- We supported advancement of consensus at WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization) towards an international legal instrument for copyright limitations and exceptions (L&Es):
 - Co-organized a major regional conference in Africa — 'A Right to Research in Africa? A Week of Debates on Copyright and Access to Knowledge', attended by legal academics, researchers, librarians, senior policy-makers and Geneva-based diplomats, to debate the copyright framework needed for modern research in Africa.
 - Supported adoption of a WIPO work programme on copyright L&Es, proposed by the African Group. The work programme provides structure and direction to future work on L&Es.

- We advocated for creation and maintenance of open public infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research in open access journals and open repositories:
 - Launched a three-year 'Collaboration for sustainable OA publishing in Africa' project with funding from Wellcome to strengthen the quality and sustainability of diamond open access publishing in Africa.
 - Our support led to improvements in the quality of 15 open access journals and repositories.
 - Coordinated the writing of COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories) 'Recommendations on managing multilingual and non-English content in repositories' and the writing of open source repository software DSpace 7 user documentation; updated and released a third version of the 'EIFL Checklist: Good practices in using Open Journal Systems software (OJS) for journal editing and publishing'.

To foster digital transformation of public library services

Major achievements in 2023 —

- We built digital literacy skills and advocated for improvements of ICT infrastructure in Uganda:
 - We completed the 'Digital skills and inclusion through libraries in Uganda' project, funded by Enabel via the Wehubit Programme (Dec 2020–June 2023), which equipped 50 librarians and library volunteers from 27 public and community libraries with new digital skills, and trained them to provide ICT training in their communities and to facilitate learning circles.

- The librarians trained over 22,000 people, mainly youth and women.
- Nearly 1,500 individuals participated in learning circles in libraries, completing online courses in a variety of topics and skills (ICT, small business management, and crafts including soap making, hairdressing, baking and sewing).
- The training programme attracted private investments in public libraries. In 2023, Airtel Uganda and the American Tower Corporation, significantly upgraded ICT infrastructure in eight public libraries.
- Continued our relationship with the Uganda Communications Commission (UCC). In 2023, UCC provided new computers, wireless internet, a printer, a scanner and a photocopier to 10 more public and community libraries.
- With partners, launched a two-year project, 'Digital Learning @ Ghana Public Libraries', with funding from the Internet Society Foundation, to open up educational and learning opportunities for school children through public libraries in Ghana.
- Organized a one-week international learning and knowledge exchange programme in Germany for four young African public library innovators from Ghana, Kenya, Namibia and Uganda to inspire them with new ideas for digital public library services.
- Announced the 17th EIFL Public Library Innovation Award call for Public Libraries addressing one of three pressing global issues: Online safety, Climate change action, and Digital rights and inclusion of forcibly displaced populations. We selected four winners, in Croatia, Kazakhstan, Kenya and Ukraine.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

This year marks the end of our 2021–2023 strategic plan. We are happy to report strong progress in achieving our goals for the period as we work towards our new plan for 2024–2026.

We celebrated the 20th anniversary of the EIFL Open Access Programme this year, and we are delighted to feature the programme's results and impact on opening up research and removing obstacles to sharing knowledge over two decades. Our plans for the next three years include more open science policies, infrastructures, training and support for no-fee open access (OA) publishing (known as Diamond OA).

Through the EIFL Licensing Programme, we paid special attention to removing financial barriers to publishing OA articles in journals that charge Article Processing Charges (APCs). By 2023, we had 14 agreements with publishers, allowing authors in EIFL partner countries to publish in OA for free or at discounted APCs. From 2021–2023, according to reports from these publishers, eligible authors published almost 5,000 OA articles saving over 6.2 million USD in APCs.

The Licensing Programme also continued to negotiate with publishers for affordable access to e-resources that were well used by scholars in partner countries. The annual average number of downloads of full-text articles, e-books and e-book chapters during the period 2021–2023 was over 7 million. We will continue our efforts to reduce financial barriers to paywalled content and publishing in OA.

The EIFL Copyright and Libraries Programme advocates for the adoption of copyright laws that maximize access to content. We participated in copyright law reform processes

in 10 countries from 2021–2023, among them, Nigeria, which adopted a new copyright law in 2023. EIFL's analysis of the Nigerian law shows it to be one of the most progressive in the world with respect to provision of access to knowledge through libraries. We will continue to support national copyright law reform in partner countries.

The EIFL Public Library Innovation Programme made a significant impact on ICT infrastructure improvement in public and community libraries in Uganda, and on librarians' skills. We completed a two-and-a-half-year project that trained librarians in 27 libraries to become ICT trainers, and they trained over 22,000 people in communities across Uganda to use computers and the internet. The project attracted donations of digital equipment from the public and private sectors benefiting 34 public and community libraries. Next year, we will seek to identify partnerships in other countries in Africa in order to develop similar projects.

Thank you to everyone — our partners, our funders, board members and staff — who helped us achieve our goals and objectives over the past three years. We look forward to working with you in the next period.

RIMA KUPRYTĖ, DIRECTOR OF EIFL

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas for EIFL

FACILITATING THE OPEN SHARING OF RESEARCH

Celebrating 20 years of the EIFL Open Access Programme

Photo by Shashank Pradhan for EIFL

“EIFL’s unique ability to work with their national library consortia in over 35 developing and transition countries allows the organization to facilitate the open sharing of the wealth of research produced to create a global research commons, one of the greatest ambitions of the open access movement.”

– MELISSA HAGEMANN, BUDAPEST OPEN ACCESS INITIATIVE

EIFL was among the original signatories to the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) that coined the term open access (OA), and in 2003 we launched the Open Access Programme (EIFL-OA) to take forward the BOAI vision. We take pleasure in sharing a history of how we have worked with our national and international partners to open up research and remove barriers to sharing knowledge.

BUILDING A CULTURE OF OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN SCIENCE

“EIFL is the true global leader in promoting open and equitable access to knowledge in developing and transitional countries. Their work sets the standard for effective open access advocacy, and has resulted in millions of individuals gaining access to critical information.” — Heather Joseph, Executive Director, SPARC, which co-organizes Open Access Week in partnership with the OA Week Advisory Committee.

“Before any major change in open access could take place, an understanding of the evolution, meaning, and importance of the practice had to be taught,” recalls Anna Chulyan, Director of the National Library of Armenia, and EIFL Country Coordinator in Armenia.

Our early work focused on advocacy, awareness raising and training. Our aim was to foster a culture of OA and open science in our partner countries, and to build the knowledge and skills needed to develop OA policies and to set up OA infrastructures — the open repositories and open journal platforms needed to enable OA to research outputs.

In July 2004, we organized our first OA event, a national workshop in Pretoria, South Africa. We followed this with workshops in Lithuania and

Poland, reaching policy-makers and academics in Central and Eastern Europe. Over the next two years, we intensified our advocacy and awareness raising efforts, with events in several more countries, including Bulgaria, China, Serbia and Slovenia.

We organized a regional OA event in South Africa in 2006, for nine Southern African countries. In 2007 we organized the first OA event in West Africa, with participants from Ghana and Nigeria; our work in eastern Africa began with national workshops in Ethiopia in 2008 and Kenya in 2010.

The impact of these events was profound. Agava Stanislaus, National Secretary of the Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC) and University Librarian at the National Intelligence and Research University College, recalled the impact of the 2010 workshop in Kenya: “The workshop sparked the interest and curiosity of researchers, students, university administrators, journal editors and librarians from institutions across Kenya. It facilitated the sharing of knowledge and insights about the potential of open access, setting the stage for the transformation that was to follow,” he says.

With growing confidence, our national library consortia partners began conducting advocacy and awareness raising campaigns at their own institutions.

We encouraged libraries to join in International Open Access Week celebrations. The first OA Week was co-organized by EIFL in 2009, and OA Week has become an annual celebration for the international OA movement. Every year we receive news of creative celebrations in our partner countries.

THE IMPORTANCE OF OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES

“EIFL’s open access programme has had a significant impact since it began 20 years ago, leading to the adoption of OA policies and implementation strategies in many institutions across the global South and other regions.”

— Leslie Chan, Associate Professor at the University of Toronto Scarborough.

We recognized early on that policies would be the key to establishing OA as the norm in our partner countries. And so, from the start, we provided advice on policy to universities, research organizations and funders; we participated in policy discussions and offered policy guidelines and templates.

Although policy development and adoption processes take time, there has been remarkable progress in our partner countries. At the end of 2017 we celebrated a policy milestone — 100 national and / or institutional OA policies adopted. Today, just six years later, that number has almost doubled, to 189.

In 2021, UNESCO’s 193 member states formally adopted the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science — the first-ever international standard for open science. EIFL participated in the development of the Recommendation through an inclusive global consultative process, and Iryna Kuchma, EIFL-OA Manager, was one of 30 international experts appointed by the UNESCO Director General to serve on the Advisory Committee that prepared the draft recommendation.

The Recommendation has sparked the revision of existing policies as well as the formulation of new ones, and we expect many more open science policies to be adopted in our partner countries in the coming years.

“EIFL has been an instrumental partner in developing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and is at the core of the global efforts focusing on its implementation,” says Ana Peršič, Programme Specialist, Open Science, Science, Technology and Innovation Policy, Natural Sciences Sector, UNESCO.

ESTABLISHING OPEN ACCESS INFRASTRUCTURES

Open access repositories

“EIFL has been a valued partner, both in terms of bringing diverse voices into the COAR working groups, but also helping to convene the right players around the table in different countries to progress open access policies and repository infrastructure.” — Kathleen Shearer, Executive Director, Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR).

In 2005, with support from EIFL, the University of Zimbabwe launched the first institutional OA repository in the EIFL network. Today 13 institutions in Zimbabwe have OA repositories. “It has become standard practice that students’ theses and dissertations are deposited in the institutional repositories,” says Blessing Chiparausha, Librarian at Bindura University of Science Education and EIFL OA Coordinator in Zimbabwe.

In 2008, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) launched an institutional OA repository, the first in Ghana and in West Africa. “When EIFL first became involved in Ghana in 2003, institutional capacity for sharing and publishing research in OA in Ghana did not exist,” recalls Richard Bruce Lamptey, Librarian at the College of Science Library at KNUST and EIFL Country Coordinator in Ghana. Since 2008, OA in

Ghana has flourished, and today there are 27 institutional OA repositories.

In many countries, establishment of just one institutional OA repository produced a snowball effect. By the end of 2008 there were over 100 OA repositories in EIFL partner countries, disseminating half a million research publications. By the end of 2017 there were over 1,000 repositories, providing OA to millions of research publications.

The most commonly used repository software in our partner countries is the free and open source software, DSpace. To help repository managers, administrators and librarians to maintain and improve their DSpace repositories we developed (and regularly update) a checklist, 'How to make your OA Repository Work Really Well'.

Open access journals

"EIFL has facilitated the development of thousands of open access journals and repositories, as well as influenced policy-making at a national and international level. DOAJ also benefits directly from EIFL's expertise and advice through their participation in our Council." — Joanna Ball, Managing Director, Directory of Open Access Journals, (DOAJ).

In 2003, print was the predominant mode of publishing in our partner countries. Very few journals were published online or in OA.

Among the first of our partner countries to launch an OA journals portal was Serbia, where EIFL-supported advocacy and awareness raising workshops led to the launch of an OA journals portal at the National Library in 2005.

By 2016, the number of Serbian scholarly journals that were freely available online had grown. However, the transition to e-publishing was incomplete — Serbian OA journals were basically traditional print journals with online versions, often in PDF format, recalls Milica Ševkušić, librarian at the Institute of Technical Sciences of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and EIFL OA Coordinator in Serbia.

To address this situation EIFL supported a 10-month project, working with our partner library consortium, KoBSON, and the National Library of Serbia.

"This project improved the quality of publishing practices and raised awareness of the importance of journal policies, Creative Commons licences and meeting the standards needed for inclusion in international directories, for example, the DOAJ," says Milica.

Today, 400 Serbian journals are published in OA, with over 200 listed in the DOAJ. "For local scholarly publishing open access is the default option. Usage statistics reveal that the content in Serbian is read all over the world, as well as that scholarly works are used beyond narrow academic circles, which encourages researchers to open up their publications," says Milica.

In 2021 we funded projects in five countries (Ethiopia, Georgia, Ghana, Kenya and Lesotho), improving the skills of journal publishers, editors and managers, and increasing and improving OA journal publishing. To increase visibility and accessibility of journals and to enhance their reputation, we encouraged good practices to ensure that journals would be eligible for indexing in international directories.

To support journal publishing, we produced (and regularly update) the 'EIFL checklist of good practices in using Open Journal Systems software (OJS) for journal editing and publishing'.

OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN SCIENCE TRAINING

"EIFL has played a significant role in developing Open Access capabilities globally, fostering intercultural understanding, and establishing collaborative learning environments." — Natalia Manola, CEO, OpenAIRE

Over the past 20 years, EIFL OA and open science training have reached over 300,000 scholars, researchers, research administrators, librarians, journal publishers and editors. To ensure the future sustainability of OA and open science training we have trained trainers and contributed to the development of courses,

manuals, guides and toolkits that are freely available online.

From 2014 to 2019 we led and coordinated the training for the EU-funded FOSTER (Facilitating Open Science Training for European Researchers) project, working with project partners. The training reached 14,000 people, mostly early career researchers, in 41 countries. Among the achievements of the FOSTER project was the development of a portal with a wide range of e-learning and training resources.

We also co-chair the Training and Support Standing Committee in OpenAIRE, which launched OpenAIRE Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps in 2022. The committee developed the OpenAIRE online training platform and material, which EIFL has used for its own bootcamps. In 2023 EIFL-OA organized two five-day open science train-the-trainer bootcamps for librarians, research staff and others who were delivering or planning to deliver open science training. The bootcamps were extremely popular — 136 trainers from across EIFL's network enrolled — and feedback was overwhelmingly positive.

"The training enhanced my knowledge and skills in open science and in developing training materials on open science. I intend to use what I learnt for teaching undergraduate and postgraduate students," said a participant from Mzuzu University in Malawi.

"This bootcamp has provided me with valuable knowledge and an opportunity to take a fresh look at the training we offer to the university community," said a participant from the Kaunas University of Technology in Lithuania.

EIFL-OA also encourages the development and integration of open science and research data management (RDM) in university courses for postgraduate students.

In Lithuania, with a grant from EIFL, Kaunas University of Technology Library developed an accredited online RDM course for PhD students.

In Estonia, the University of Tartu, and several other universities, academic libraries and

research organizations now offer courses in open science and open data. "These courses demonstrate the institutions' commitment to fostering open science and research data management skills among PhD students. Based on feedback, it can be emphasized that early career researchers are very willing to practice open science," says Elena Sipria-Mironov, librarian at the University of Tartu Library and EIFL OA Coordinator in Estonia.

20 YEARS OF EIFL-OA IN NUMBERS —

19 national and **189** institutional open access and open science policies.

1,200+ open access repositories.

4,100+ open access journals.

312,900+ people trained from 2004 - 2023.

CONTRIBUTION TO THE GLOBAL OA MOVEMENT

Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) — original signatory

Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) — founding member

Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS) — founding member

OpenAIRE AMKE — founding member

Open Access Week — founding member

Thank you to everyone who contributed to our 20th Anniversary celebrations, and thank you to Arcadia, the European Commission, Open Society Foundations, SPIDER (the Swedish Programme for ICT in Developing Regions) and Wellcome for supporting the EIFL Open Access Programme over the years.

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives and the lives of others

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas for EIFL

DR DESMOND ORIAKHOGBA

**BARRISTER AND SOLICITOR OF
THE SUPREME COURT OF NIGERIA,
SENIOR LECTURER, FACULTY OF LAW,
UNIVERSITY OF THE WESTERN CAPE,
SOUTH AFRICA**

NIGERIA

Nigeria's Copyright Act, 2022, adopted in March 2023, is one of the most progressive in the world with respect to libraries.

EIFL was active in the lawmaking process — providing inspiration for the library provisions, commenting on the draft text, and writing to the President of Nigeria urging its early adoption. Dr Oriakhogba presented EIFL's comments on the draft law at a public hearing organized by the Nigerian Senate in 2021.

“The new Copyright Act captures the essence of copyright — it rewards and recognizes creators while ensuring fair access to creative works by the public. The strong body of limitations and exceptions create a very broad space for librarians to carry out their daily work without fear of being sued for copyright infringement,” says Dr Oriakhogba, “for example, the right to make and distribute copies for education and research, people with print disabilities (Nigeria ratified the Marrakesh Treaty in 2017), and preservation (essential for out-of-print, damaged and valuable materials).

“The law also voids licence terms that might limit these library rights, a very important element to support librarians not familiar with the intricacies of copyright and contract law,” continued Dr Oriakhogba.

“Now libraries should take full advantage. The Copyright Commission of Nigeria has started to raise awareness of the new law, and EIFL's guide, 'What can Libraries in Nigeria do under the 2022 Copyright Act?', is an excellent resource.”

“The library exceptions in the Copyright Act, 2022 are modelled on EIFL’s Draft Law on Copyright. EIFL can be proud of the impact they are making in Africa.”

– DR DESMOND ORIAKHOGBA

ZORICA JANKOVIĆ

**LIBRARIAN, INSTITUTE FOR
BIOLOGICAL RESEARCH 'SINIŠA
STANKOVIĆ', UNIVERSITY OF
BELGRADE
SERBIA**

After almost 10 years of providing open access and research data management training for researchers, Zorica Janković realized that she needed to learn new open science training methods and to find new training tools.

“Our researchers need training to help them understand how open science practices attract new collaborations. There is a fear of openness. They also need to understand the importance of research data management (RDM) planning, which is one of the central components of open science.

“I was trying to get these messages across in my training sessions with groups of up to 10 researchers. But in each group I could see at least one person was not convinced. And that is why I joined the EIFL Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp.”

The EIFL bootcamp took place online, in November 2023, and ran over five half days. The invitation targeted open science trainers — librarians, research support staff and other professionals — in EIFL partner countries. A total of 52 trainers from 19 countries took part.

“The training was very good for me,” said Zorica. “It was organized in a way that was completely new to me. There were games to arouse interest, to help scientists overcome their trust issues, to solve problems and to believe in open science as a positive innovation. And the training materials have been really useful.”

In December 2023 Zorica was selected to be part of a team of trainers for a RDM workshop for researchers and librarians of major research institutes in Serbia. The workshop drew on the training methods and materials tested during the EIFL bootcamp. The workshop participants now have ambitious plans for the future, including an open science bootcamp in Serbia and developing a self-paced course on open science in Serbian.

“I learnt how to integrate real-life examples into my training. After the bootcamp I invited a scientist who practices open science methods to speak to one of my training groups, from a scientist’s perspective. This worked really well.”

– ZORICA JANKOVIĆ

Photo by Maj Blatnik (NUK)

MARIKA MELTSAS

PROJECT MANAGER, CONSORTIUM OF ESTONIAN LIBRARIES NETWORK ESTONIA

EIFL's partner library consortium, the Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET), is currently the only organization conducting central negotiations for affordable access to e-resources for all of Estonia's six public research universities and seven universities of applied sciences, as well as all publicly-funded and evaluated research institutions.

ELNET joined the EIFL network in 1999, and is one of EIFL's oldest partners. "Some years ago, most of the e-resources (research databases, online journals, e-books) were negotiated by EIFL. But today, out of the 30 e-resources available through ELNET, just three were negotiated by EIFL. Access to the other 27 e-resources we negotiated with publishers ourselves," says Marika Meltsas.

Marika attributes ELNET's success in negotiations to EIFL. "We learnt how to negotiate through EIFL's training and resources. For me, the best training has been practical, in which we have the opportunity to interact with publishers. In our interactions with publishers we are guided by EIFL's principles for negotiations, and EIFL's model agreements."

The e-resources are very well used, says Marika. "Over 80% of content used by scholars at the institutions that ELNET covers is still behind the paywall, so the content that we negotiate and can make accessible in the most cost-effective way is valued by our members."

Recently, ELNET has begun entering into Read & Publish (R&P) agreements with publishers. R&P agreements provide access to scholarly journals while at the same time allowing authors to publish in open access for free or at discounted Article Processing Charges (APCs).

In 2023 ELNET had five R&P agreements. "We are watching trends to see how these R&P agreements impact open access publishing at our member institutions," says Marika.

"EIFL has set standards for negotiations and agreements with publishers to ensure our scholars have the maximum access to the resources they need for research and education."

– MARIKA MELTSAS

VIOLA OBIRU

TAILORING INSTRUCTOR UGANDA

Young, unemployed and worried about her future, Viola Obiru from Koboko town in Uganda jumped at the opportunity to learn digital skills at her local library.

"I heard about the training from a friend and I was desperate to learn digital skills, because now everything is digitized. And I hoped the training would help me to find work.

"I was very committed — I attended daily three-hour sessions, Mondays to Saturdays, for three months. Peterlee, the librarian, was an inspiring and supportive trainer," says Viola.

Koboko Public Library was one of 27 libraries that participated in the Digital Skills @ Your Local Library project, implemented by EIFL and partners in Uganda from 2020 to 2023.

The project built librarians' digital and training skills so that they could offer ICT training in their communities and connect learners to online courses. The libraries trained over 22,000 people in basic digital skills; in addition, 1,500 people completed online courses in entrepreneurial and technical skills, craft-making and other subjects, learning in groups facilitated by librarians.

Viola became a team leader for the library's trainees. "My role was to encourage the class to learn. One method I used was an online quiz. To compete, the trainees had to give answers to the questions via email."

After completing her ICT training, Viola took an online course in tailoring, using the library's computers. She is now employed as an instructor at an industrial training centre, providing tailoring training to women. "I also have a small business producing clothes and empowering vulnerable girls and women — orphans, early school leavers and single parents — so that they can become independent like me."

"I bring my trainees to the library for digital training, so that they can also take online courses, to learn and be more secure in future."

— VIOLA OBIRU

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

We would like to thank all our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2023.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo
Open Access Coordinator: Renata Bardhi

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Licensing Coordinators: Tatevik Tamazyan
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library and Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country Coordinators: Jamila Yusifova and Itifat Ibrahimov
Licensing Coordinator: Itifat Ibrahimov

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing: Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Poloko Ntokwane

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu
Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwangane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Côte d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou Ouffouet
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo Epse Outtara

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Girma Aweke
Licensing Coordinators: Bedassa Motuma Beyene
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Open Access Coordinator: Getnet Lemma

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udy Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country, Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Nino Pavliashvili
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Open Access Coordinators: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufu Quagraine

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Janegrace Kinyanjui (until June); Paul Gichohi (from June)
Open Access Coordinator: George Njoroge (until June); Stanislaus Agava (from June)

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELK)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Tolgonai Kozhokanova

LAOS

Laos Library and Information Consortium (LALIC)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Sypha Phongsavath
Open Access Coordinator: Sisavanh Linsavath

LATVIA

Culture Information Systems Centre

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Agrita Sagalajeva
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Buhle Mbambo-Thata
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Nkuebe
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Jevgenija Sevcova
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country Coordinator: Patrick Mapulanga
Licensing Coordinator: Trevor Namondwe
Copyright Coordinator: Blessings Katuma
Open Access Coordinator: Chifundo Chipendo

MALDIVES

(No name — under development)

Country Coordinator: Zulhana Adam
Licensing Coordinator: Majidha Ali

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Elena Tudor Railean

Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi

Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country & Copyright Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks

Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Miodrag Dadasovic

Open Access Coordinator: Rozita Petrinska Labudovikj (until July)

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser; Rami Alhindawi for Gaza

Licensing Coordinator: Mohammad Abu Hamdieh

Open Access Coordinator: Asad Tom

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye

Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse

Open Access Coordinators: Djibril Diallo, Abdoulaye Gueye and Mangaty Sakho

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic

Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic and Boris Denadic

Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic

Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek

Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj

Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman

Licensing Coordinator: Babelshafia Makki (from December)

Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Abdelaziz Gabir (until December)

Open Access Coordinator: Rania M. Hassan Baleela

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul Samwel Muneja

Licensing Coordinator: Cyrill Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (eifl-Thailand)

Country, Copyright and Licensing Coordinator: Soeythip Sukul

Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya

Licensing Coordinator: Drake Tamale

Copyright Coordinator: Eric Haumba

Open Access Coordinator: Hassan Ssengooba

UKRAINE

Association 'Informatio-Consortium'

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliiev

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Husniya Boysunova

Licensing Coordinator: Alisher Kattabekov

Open Access Coordinator: Maksim Savochkin (until July); Gulbakhor Kabiljanova (from July)

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness Chitumbo

Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu

Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Sarlomie Zinyemba

Copyright Coordinator: Rosemary Maturure

Open Access Coordinator: Blessing Chiparausha

OUR TEAM

The EIFL General Assembly (GA) 2023 took place in Vilnius, Lithuania, from 18–20 September. We were very happy to meet in-person for the first time after three years of online meetings to help restrict the spread of COVID-19. Photo by Augustinas Žukovas for EIFL.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager

Dick Kawooya, Coordinator of Copyright Advocacy in Africa, Right to Research Project

Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator

Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager

Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager, Website and Publications

Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator

Lorraine Estelle, Licensing Programme Manager

Louise Stoddard, Communications Manager

Milica Ševkušić, Open Access Programme, Project Coordinator

Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager

Rima Kuprytė, Director

Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager

Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Emilija Banionytė, Chairperson, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania

Adam Hyde, Founder of Coko, Book Sprints, Paged.js, Open Publishing Awards and the Open Publishing Fest

Colleen Campbell, Max Planck Digital Library, Max Planck Society, Germany

David Bukenya, Uganda Christian University (from August)

Joel Sam, African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AFLIA), Ghana (until August)

Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL INCOME AND EXPENDITURE 2023

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	2,350,599	71.3 %
• Participation fees	544,447	16.5 %
• General Support	371,772	11.3 %
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	28,772	0.9 %
Total	3,295,590	

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	893,759	88.1 %
• Personnel & contracted expenses	100,034	9.9 %
• Operating expenses	20,047	2.0 %
Total	1,013,840	

**COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR
2024–2026 PROGRAMME DELIVERY** 2,267,091

CONTINUITY RESERVE 284,190

OUR FUNDERS

ORGANIZATIONS

We would like to thank the following organizations for their generous support for our work in 2023:

- Arcadia Fund through the American University / Washington College of Law, and the Creative Commons Corporation
- Bibliothek & Information Deutschland (BID)
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- European Commission Erasmus+ Programme through Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework Programme through OpenAIRE AMKE
- European Commission Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
- Internet Society Foundation through TechSoup Global
- LEGO Foundation
- Open Society Foundations
- University of Luxembourg (UNILU)
- Wehubit Programme (implemented by the Belgian development agency, Enabel)

EVENTS

In 2023, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 94 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Webinar: Supporting Ukrainian Refugees with Print Disabilities (Online)
- Panel on public libraries and sustainable development at the II Feria Internacional del Libro Biobío (Online)
- Training skills for Laos law faculty (Vientiane, Lao People's Democratic Republic)
- A Right to Research in Africa? Conference on Copyright and Access to Knowledge (Pretoria & Cape Town, South Africa, and Online)
- EIFL Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- Policy Brief Launch: The Right to Research and Copyright Law in Kenya: Text and Data Mining (Online)
- WIPO Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (SCCR/43) (Geneva, Switzerland, and Online)
- What is the role of model laws in norm setting for intellectual property? WIPO SCCR/43 Side Event (Geneva, Switzerland)
- WACREN 2023 Conference "Tooling Up for the African Digital Learner and Researcher" (Accra, Ghana)

FEBRUARY

- Open Climate Campaign project partners meeting (New York, USA)
- The African Librarysites Platform: Official Launch and Orientation (Online)
- 3rd Open Science Conference (New York, USA, and Online)
- EOSC Future project meeting (Pisa, Italy)
- Botswana University of Agriculture and Natural Resources institutional repository launch (Online)
- AMICAL Consortium Webinar: Open research: Why it's important, how to make research more open and how to drive change (Online)
- 'Digital skills@your local library' project's knowledge sharing meeting (Kampala, Uganda)
- Research Data Alliance (RDA) 20th Plenary Meeting (Gothenburg, Sweden, and Online)
- SCOSS Webinar: Keeping open infrastructure open (Online)
- National Open Science Cloud Initiative launch event in Moldova (Chişinău, Moldova, and Online)

APRIL

- OpenAIRE coffee break on the University of Vienna certificate course "Data Steward" (Online)
- The UKSG 46th Annual Conference (Glasgow, United Kingdom)
- P2PU Community Call on Digital Inclusion (Online)
- Workshop Promoting Access to Knowledge and the Right to Research in Kenya (Nairobi, Kenya, and Online)
- SCILLS 2023 Info session (Online)

MAY

- RetrainPlus Community of Practice Meeting: EOSC Portal and Marketplace (Online)
- Webinar: OA journal publishing in Georgia (Online)
- Next Library 2023: International Library Festival (Aarhus, Denmark, and Online)
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) Annual Meeting 2023 (San José, Costa Rica)
- 3rd OpenAIRE Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- Library week in Kosovo (Pristina, Kosovo)
- 5th AfLIA Conference & 7th African Library Summit (Accra, Ghana, and Online)
- XVI International Conference 'Central Asia — 2023 : Information and Library resources in science, education, culture and business' (Bukhara, Uzbekistan)
- Open Science Forum (Novi Sad, Serbia)

JUNE

- Dataverse Community Meeting 2023 (Braga, Portugal)
- 16th Berlin Open Access Conference (Berlin, Germany)
- OpenAIRE coffee-break on e-accessibility: It's all about the tools (Online)
- Open Repositories 2023 Conference (Somerset West, South Africa)
- Training course 'Access to Knowledge in the Multilateral System' (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Webinar: How to make your research products discoverable in the EOSC Portal (Online)

- Webinar: The most important elements of successful research proposal (Online)
- PoISCA (Polish Science Contact Agency) Webinar: Open Science in practice (Online)
- 'Digital skills @ your local project library visits (Kabale, Kitengesa, Masaka, Mbarara and Nyarushanje in Uganda)
- EOSC Future Train-the-trainer active learning course (Online)
- Webinar: How to make sure that your EOSC service is up and running (Online)
- Webinar: Celebrating 10 years of the Marrakesh Treaty (Online)

JULY

- Diamond Open Access in Europe and beyond workshop (Budapest, Hungary)
- WIPO Annual Assemblies 2023 (Geneva, Switzerland, and Online)
- Webinar: Libraries & the Global Digital Compact (Online)
- Data Skills Training Workshop in Zimbabwe (Filabusi, Zimbabwe, and Online)

AUGUST

- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Becoming a super-searcher (Online)
- IFLA Libraries for Children and Young Adults Section: Quarterly meeting (Online)
- IFLA WLIC 2023 Satellite meeting: Agile Methodology in Libraries: Innovations in Library Projects and Management (Online)
- Asia Pacific Advanced Network APAN56 Conference (Colombo, Sri Lanka, and Online)

SEPTEMBER

- Young African Library Innovators study tour to Germany (Bremen, Cologne, Frankfurt, Germany)
- OAI13 — The Geneva Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (Online)
- University of Maribor Open Science Summer School (Online)
- Wehubit Days: Project Partners' meeting (Kigali, Rwanda)
- EOSC Future Train-the-trainer active learning course (Online)
- OASPA Webinar: Scholarly communication's response to the climate crisis and the role of open science (Online)
- Webinar: Share your Training Resources on the EOSC Portal (Online)
- 2023 EIFL General Assembly (Vilnius, Lithuania)
- Open Access Talk: The Open Climate Campaign (Online)
- Open Science FAIR 2023 (Madrid, Spain)
- 12th OpenAIRE General Assembly (Madrid, Spain)

OCTOBER

- Internet Society Foundation: SCILLS funded projects kick-off meeting (Online)
- IGF 2023 DC-PAL session 'Public Access evolutions — lessons from the last 20 years' (Kyoto, Japan, and Online)
- Webinar: Diamond Open Access for publishers from Balkan countries (Online)
- OPTIMA Workshop on best practices on open science and OER (Graz, Austria)
- Webinar: HeinOnline product updates (Online)
- The Periodicals and a Changing Society Conference, Lithuania (Online)

- Global Summit on Diamond Open Access (Toluca, Mexico, and Online)
- Open Access Week 2023 (Global)
- OA Week 2023 event in North Macedonia (Skopje, North Macedonia, and Online)
- OA Week 2023 webinar in Zimbabwe (Gweru, Zimbabwe, and Online)
- Lecture to LIS students of the University of Illinois Urbana Champaign, School of Information Sciences: EIFL-PLIP: An International perspective to public library transformation (Online)
- Open Access Week 2023 events in Botswana (Gaborone, Botswana, and Online)
- II International Conference 'Open Science and Innovation in Ukraine 2023' (Online)
- Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC) Open Access Week 2023 webinar (Online)
- British Library's Open and Engaged Conference 2023 (London, United Kingdom, and Online)

NOVEMBER

- EOSC Festival 2023. The National Tripartite Event Poland (Krakow, Poland, and Online)
- WIPO Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (SCCR/44) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- EIFL Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- UKSG November Conference 2023 (Online)
- COAR Webinar: Good Practices in Asian Repositories (Online)
- 4th OpenAIRE Open Science Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- Webinar: Crossref Services for Librarians and Journal Editors (Online)
- Webinar: SCOSS Invites (Online)

DECEMBER

- Webinar: Best practices in diamond OA (Online)
- Summit of Chief Negotiators (Online)
- Webinar: scite.ai (Online)
- 'Integrity, Open Science and AI in Academia and Beyond: Meeting at the Crossroads' Conference (Online)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2023, we worked with the following partners:

- Access to Knowledge (A2K) Coalition
- African Journals Online (AJOL)
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AFLIA)
- American University Washington College of Law, Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property (PIJIP)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries
- Black Stripe Foundation
- Bremen City Library
- Center for International Property and Information Technology Law (CIPIT), Strathmore University
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- Coalition Publi.ca
- Coalition S
- CODATA
- Coko Foundation
- Cologne City Library
- COMMUNIA Association
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Corporación Innovarte
- Coventry University
- Creative Commons
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), Lyrasis
- Education International
- EOSC Association
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- Federal Association of German Library and Information Associations (BID)
- Frankfurt City Library
- Gigabit Library Network (GLN)
- Ghana Library Authority
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- Information Power
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Council of Museums (ICOM)
- International Council on Archives (ICA)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- International Union for Conservation of Nature
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Ecology International (KEI)
- Leva Foundation
- Libraries Development, Local Government Management Agency Ireland
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- LIBSENSE
- Lithuanian Audiosensory Library
- Lithuanian Research Libraries Consortium
- Maendeleo Foundation
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- OA Switchboard
- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)
- ORCID
- Open Society University Network (OSUN)
- OA2020
- Peer 2 Peer University
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- ReCreate South Africa
- South Centre
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- TechSoup
- The World Academy of Sciences (TWAS)
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UKSG
- UNESCO
- Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wildlife Conservation Society
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)
- Zambia Library Service

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working Relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 99 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS); European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future; Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia (OPTIMA); Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System (Open4UA) and Strengthening Research Management and Open Science Capacities of HEIs in Moldova and Armenia (Minerva).

STAY CONNECTED

[eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)

[@EIFLnet](https://twitter.com/EIFLnet)

[eifl-net](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eifl-net)

GET IN TOUCH

Mail: Mindaugo str. 23, LT-03214 Vilnius, Lithuania

Tel: +370 5 2080409 **Email:** info@eifl.net

For more information about EIFL and our work visit [eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)